

Energy-Efficient Resource Management via Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning in O-RAN

Shaoxuan Wang
Iquadrat Informatica,
Barcelona, Spain
swang@iquadrat.com

John S. Vardakas
Dept. of Informatics
UOWM, Kastoria, Greece, and
Iquadrat Informatica,
Barcelona, Spain
jvardakas@iquadrat.com

Christos Verikoukis
CEID, University of Patras,
Greece, and
ISI/ATHINA, Patras, Greece
cveri@upatras.gr

Abstract—Sixth-generation (6G) wireless networks are expected to meet all the demands of the next decade, a feasibility that is only possible with advances in network design and management. This paper first proposes a unified resource management framework for a 6G-based network architecture that includes an Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) deployment and then defines a hierarchical network energy control and resource management approach. Leveraging the openness of O-RAN, the proposed novel Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning (HRL)-based scheme provides two-level centralized agent policy evaluation and decentralized agent real-time scheduling optimization, thereby minimizing system energy consumption while ensuring Quality of Service (QoS). To validate the performance of this management approach, we propose a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based algorithm for each level. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of this solution in terms of throughput, user-experienced data rate, and energy consumption.

Index Terms—6G network, O-RAN, hierarchical reinforcement learning, scheduling optimization, policy evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the deployment of fifth-generation (5G) cellular networks, research attention has gradually shifted toward the next generation, where the limitations of 5G are expected to be addressed and emerging services supported. Sixth-generation (6G) wireless networks are expected to meet all the needs of the next decade, and this will only be possible through advances in network design and management. The evolution of mobile communication networks has been closely accompanied by continuous changes in radio access network (RAN) architectures. Through further functional decoupling, modular design, and virtualized deployment, 5G access networks have achieved adaptability to complex communication scenarios and significantly improved performance. However, existing access network architectures still face challenges such as vendor lock-in, high deployment costs, and limited upgrade flexibility, which hinder their ability to support the intelligent management requirements envisioned for 6G networks. To address these challenges, the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture has emerged as a promising alternative.

Led by the O-RAN Alliance, the O-RAN architecture aims to overcome the closed nature of traditional radio access networks through software–hardware decoupling, open interfaces, and

intelligent control, thereby enabling flexible deployment and optimization [1]. O-RAN has further split the access network elements by analysing the architecture of previous generations of wireless access networks and defined the network element interface standards. Thanks to this, base station components from different manufacturers based on the O-RAN architecture can be compatible with each other through open interfaces, breaking the supplier lock-in of the traditional model. To further enhance network intelligence, O-RAN introduces the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), which enables the deployment of learning-based algorithms for dynamic wireless resource scheduling. In O-RAN, further software and hardware decoupling and the deepening of cloud and virtualization design enable operators to quickly adapt to new business needs through software updates, thereby reducing equipment maintenance and upgrade costs [2].

Artificial intelligence (AI) has become an important paradigm for wireless network optimization due to its ability to learn from complex data and adapt to dynamic [3]. In recent years, deep learning has been increasingly used in communication technology, covering multiple areas such as channel estimation [4], signal modulation [5], and channel coding [6]. In particular, reinforcement learning techniques have been widely investigated for tasks such as resource allocation [7], [8], power control [9], and beam management [10], owing to their autonomous decision-making and adaptive optimization capabilities.

Motivated by the above observations, this paper investigates resource scheduling strategies for communication systems under the O-RAN architecture. The focus is on the intelligent scheduling strategy of communication resources and the construction and related design of the prototype system of the O-RAN architecture communication platform. In this framework, this paper provides the design of a reward function mechanism that jointly optimizes energy efficiency and resource allocation in the low-level Reinforcement Learning (RL) process. To enhance stability, Tanh-saturated reward functions are employed to prevent optimization pathologies, while adaptive weight mechanisms in both upper and lower agent layers enable dynamic multi-objective balancing.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of related work on exploiting Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) for telecommunication. Section III presents the proposed an O-RAN based network infrastructure via the design of an efficient resource scheduler, which is an efficient solution for the joint orchestration and management of computational and communication resources. Section IV describes the evaluation scenario with the different configurations being evaluated and Section V provides and discusses the simulation results of the proposed method. Finally, Section VI draws the conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

Several studies have investigated the use of RL models and their variants to address resource allocation or energy-saving services in communication networks. Specifically, the authors of [11] propose a Hierarchical Deep Reinforcement Learning (HDRL) approach for efficient spectrum allocation across terrestrial to non-terrestrial networks, DRL agents are present at each level of hierarchy that dynamically learn and allocate spectrum based on regional trends. Similarly, [12] formulates a two-level HRL model for relay selection and power allocation in cooperative relay networks, effectively decoupling discrete relay selection from continuous power control. These studies demonstrate that HRL is particularly suitable for large-scale wireless systems with heterogeneous decision horizons. However, they are designed for conventional network architectures and do not consider the multi-layer control separation inherent to O-RAN. The authors of [13] propose a solution that learns a service function chain placement policy for network slice requests, to maximize the request acceptance rate, while minimizing the average node resource utilization. The approach presented in [14] proposes a two-level intelligent slicing strategy designed to optimize resource allocation in O-RAN based 5G networks. This strategy involves conducting the allocation of RBs at the core of the network through an SDN mechanism and subsequently at the gNodeB level utilizing an O-RAN technology. A team-learning algorithm is proposed in [15] to enhance the performance of the network by increasing cooperation between xAPPs and compare the team-learning approach with independent deep Q-learning, where network functions optimize resources individually.

Although these approaches leverage O-RAN architectural features, they mainly focus on short-term radio resource optimization and do not provide a unified hierarchical framework spanning both non-real-time and near-real-time control loops. Energy efficiency has long been recognized as a critical requirement for next-generation networks. Several studies employ RL or multi-agent RL to jointly optimize throughput, QoS, and energy consumption. For instance, [16] presents a multi-agent RL-based resource allocation scheme that maximizes network energy efficiency while maintaining communication quality. Survey work such as [17] provides a comprehensive overview of DRL-based resource scheduling in MEC environments, emphasizing the importance of coordinated computing-communication optimization. Nevertheless, most existing

Fig. 1: System Model.

solutions either consider energy efficiency in isolation or rely on flat control architectures, limiting their applicability to O-RAN systems with hierarchical control requirements.

From the above discussion, although HRL has been explored for wireless resource management and learning-based methods have been applied within O-RAN environments, existing works do not jointly address energy efficiency and fine-grained resource allocation within O-RAN's multi-layer control architecture. This gap motivates the proposed hierarchical reinforcement learning framework, which explicitly integrates long-term energy-aware policy evaluation at the Non-RT RIC with real-time decentralized scheduling at the Near-RT RIC. The contributions of this work are as follows:

- We propose a reward function mechanism based on the coordination of energy efficiency and resource allocation in low level RL.
- We propose tanh-saturated reward functions, preventing optimization pathologies in the low level agent.
- We implement an adaptive weight mechanism in upper and lower layers of agents to achieve dynamic multi-objective balance.

III. UNIFIED 6G NETWORK RESOURCE MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

A. System model description

The proposed solution aims to provide a unified network management framework by enabling the joint orchestration and management of computational and communication resources. The system model follows the O-RAN specification, where the non-real-time RIC is located in the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO), as shown in Fig. 1. In mid-haul networks, the Near Real-time (Near-RT) RIC is responsible for real-time operations related to radio resource management and O-RU cluster formation (based on the CSI collected from the O-DU). Furthermore, a non-real-time (Non-RT) RIC resides in the

SMO and is responsible for long-term control and optimization functions. This non-RT RIC connects to the Near-Real-Time (NRT) RIC via the A1 interface. The SMO connects to the O-RAN cloud (O-cloud) and the O-DU using the O2 and O1 interfaces, respectively. Interface E2 connects the O-CU and O-DU to the Near-Real-Time (Near RT) RIC, and the O-CU manages the O-DU via interface F1.

In this multi-layer network architecture, resources are distributed across different locations. The Non-RT RIC can leverage all connections from the SMO to the O-DU, O-RU, and O-cloud to gather information about the network status. Therefore, the first layer of our proposed solution, referred to as the upper-level agent in the rest of this paper, will reside in the non-real-time RIC. At this layer, a DRL set will observe the network system and available resources for meeting global user Quality-of-Service (QoS) assessment, and then apply joint upper-level policies and actions based on their observations and collaboration will be taken.

The Near-RT RIC is connected to the Non-RT RIC through the A1 interface and hosts the second level of the proposed scheme, referred to as the lower-level agent. At this stage, a single agent performs decentralized execution, while centralized decisions at the upper level ensure resource availability. Each agent receives a selected service type from an upper-level agent and tries to allocate resources to this type. Since nearby RICs are also connected to O-CU and O-DU, the latter modules are responsible for dealing with O-RUs and users. Thus, the lower-level part can benefit from these connections to assign the resource blocks in the network entities.

By introducing two operational layers, two corresponding scheduling timescales are naturally defined. Therefore, we consider long time-slots at the decision level, while short time-slots are considered for the execution level. Inevitably, long time-slots are within the control loop provided by the non-RT RIC (more than 1 s) while short time-slots are limited by the near RT RIC control loop (between 10 ms and 1 s). At the same time, O-RUs provide connectivity for end users, assuming that fixed paths to allocate resources cannot be considered a realistic assumption. To solve this complex problem, in each new long time-slot, the request will be related to the new performance determined by the agent. It is worth mentioning that ensuring resource availability is only effective if lower-level tasks are the best results and individual agents meet the lower and upper limits.

B. Implementation Technicalities

This section illustrates how HRL is applied to the proposed system model. The technical details of the implementation are presented in Fig. 2; the two-level agent architecture are presented as follows: *Upper-level Agent*: As mentioned earlier, since the layout of 6G networks is still under research and discussion, we consider the three main service types currently available in 5G in this paper. Thus, according to the service types suggested in [18], three representative service types are considered: enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-

Fig. 2: The proposed approach: Two-Level Energy-Aware Resource Orchestration Architecture.

Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC), and massive Internet of Things (mIoT).

The number of upper-level agents depends on the number of tenants and service types that must be supported simultaneously in the network. This is because each agent receives one request during each longer time period, so the total number of requests received is equal to the number of agents. Next, we consider 3 service brokers which is acting as input data in Fig. 2 in the multi agent RL set to estimate an equal number of requests for each service type over each longer time period. Therefore, the total number of requests received is equal to the number of agents. Each agent's observation includes, in addition to the type of service available, a request. This request can be just one or a combination of several defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (i.e., throughput, user data rate, and energy efficiency). Following the goal of maximizing network throughput, the agent will coordinate with the requests and decisions of other agents to make the best choice to achieve better results. Each agent will try to find a suitable service type for the request. This means that if there are no resources in the system for the requested service type, no allocation will be made. Therefore, the upper-level agent is responsible for global resource analysis, long-term policy training, and the formulation of high-level resource allocation strategies. For example, determining the resource quota ratio for each user.

Meanwhile, if agents are assigned the correct service type or wait if no service is available, they will receive their respective rewards. However, the overall joint objective at this level is to maximize the utilization of available resources and the network's energy efficiency. Therefore, the final reward is a combination of each agent's individual reward and the team's reward based on the amount of resources allocated at the end

of a long time period. We consider increasing the final reward ratio of the joint goal to encourage the allocation of more resources while guiding the agent's decision making. Therefore, the upper-level reward is calculated as follows:

$$R_{\text{team}} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{1}{3} * R_{\text{individual},i}(t) + \frac{2}{3} * R_{\text{collective}}(t) \right) \quad (1)$$

$$R_{\text{collective}}(t) = \min \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 \text{Resource}_i(t)}{\text{Resource}_{\text{total}}}, 1.0 \right) \quad (2)$$

in which $R_{\text{individual},i}(t)$ is equal to 1 if the assigned resources are available for service i at time t . Otherwise, the reward is 0. At the same time, $R_{\text{collective}}(t)$ is the ratio of resources in-use to all resources at time t . This means that the more resources you use, the higher the return. The considered ratio is the final decision after many trials with different ratios.

Lower-level agent: In the upper-level part, the multi-agent ensemble tries to maximize the network throughput by selecting the appropriate service type for the request, while the agents in the lower-level part are responsible for providing the QoS for each user type by allocating resource over longer time steps. To achieve this goal, each agent tries to allocate available resources with shorter time steps. In other words, by defining appropriate lower and upper bounds on the action space, the agent applies an allocation strategy that keeps all KPIs defining that service type within appropriate ranges. Therefore, the role of the low-level agent is to carry out specific resource allocation and energy loss control under the guidance of upper-level strategies, integrate energy-aware reward functions, monitor network status in real time, quickly infer scheduling strategies, and issue execution instructions to meet the goals set by upper-level strategies. Finally, the lower-level reward function is defined as follows:

$$R_{\text{low}}(t) = w_{\text{throughput}} * R_{\text{throughput}}(t) + w_{\text{energy}} * R_{\text{energy}}(t) + w_{\text{QoS}} * R_{\text{QoS}}(t) \quad (3)$$

$$R_{\text{throughput}}(t) = \frac{\text{Throughput}_{\text{total}}(t)}{\text{Throughput}_{\text{baseline}}} \quad (4)$$

$$R_{\text{QoS}}(t) = \frac{1}{2} (1 + \tanh(10 * (QoS_{\text{rate}}(t) - 0.7))) \quad (5)$$

in which, $R_{\text{low}}(t)$ is the total reward of low-level agent, and consists of different parts, they are $R_{\text{throughput}}$, R_{energy} and R_{QoS} , and each of which is a linear combination of the corresponding weighted values w . A tanh-based QoS reward smooths deviations and stabilizes training. The upper-level runs at the Non-RT RIC for long-timescale coordination, while the lower-level runs at the Near-RT RIC for near-real-time inference-based scheduling, avoiding cross-layer synchronous optimization.

IV. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

This work adopts a data-driven evaluation using O-RAN-related dataset and emulates the statistical characteristics of network observations for algorithmic assessment, rather than full protocol-level or event-driven simulations with explicit control-loop timing. The evaluation environment is implemented in Python using PyTorch 2.0+ for deep learning, together with standard scientific computing libraries such as NumPy, SciPy, and Pandas for data processing, and Matplotlib for visualization. Gymnasium is adopted for implementing the reinforcement learning environments. The development environment includes Jupyter notebooks for interactive analysis. O-RAN is considered as a key architectural enabler for future 6G networks, within which the proposed RL-based approach can be deployed at the RIC layers. The evaluation environment emulates the statistical characteristics of network observations that would be available to learning agents, rather than performing a full system-level control-loop simulation.

Our experimental evaluation employs a large collection of O-RAN-related datasets, formed by combining the Colosseum O-RAN (ColoRAN) dataset with the O-RAN Experimental Evaluation Datasets from IEEE Data Port. This combined dataset provides authentic base station performance metrics from 12 different cellular deployments, including throughput measurements, energy consumption indices, Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) adaptations, and quality-of-service parameters collected under diverse network conditions and user scenarios.

The upper-level agent operates in an environment that interfaces with the QMIX algorithm, while the lower-level agent interacts with individual agents through Normalized Advantage Functions (NAF)-based deep Q-learning [19], [20]. The evaluation framework implements four distinct experimental phases to systematically assess our proposed approach. The upper-level coordination layer utilizes the QMIX algorithm for multi-agent service orchestration, while the lower-level resource allocation layer employs NAF for continuous control optimization. Unlike simplified synthetic simulations, the proposed evaluation incorporates realistic network performance variations and resource constraints derived from experimental datasets, enabling a data-driven assessment of the proposed hierarchical learning framework.

Our comprehensive evaluation of the proposed two-layer hierarchical RL (Dual-layer RL algorithm) framework across multiple performance dimensions is compared with the current mature baseline scheduling strategies (traditional scheduling strategies, maximum throughput strategies, minimum energy consumption strategies, balanced strategies, QoS satisfaction scheduling strategies) and the single-layer DQN method. The experimental results are shown in Fig. 3, including four dimensions: Total Throughput, Per-User Rate, Energy Efficiency Factor (EEF), and QoS Satisfaction Rate.

EEF is a metric, which measures the energy efficiency of a system when transmitting data at a certain throughput. Higher values indicate greater throughput per unit of energy consumed,

meaning greater energy efficiency. The QoS Satisfaction Rate measures the degree to which users' Quality of Service meets the standard, considering factors such as throughput, MCS, and latency. A higher value means more users meet the standard. Finally, these two parameters are calculated as follows:

$$EEF = \frac{E_{\text{baseline}}}{\max(E_{UL} + E_{DL}, 0.1)} \quad (6)$$

$$QoS_rate = 0.5 * S_{\text{throughput}} + 0.3 * S_{\text{mcs}} + 0.2 * S_{\text{latency}} \quad (7)$$

$$S_{\text{throughput}} = \min\left(\frac{\text{total throughput}}{0.8}, 1.0\right) \quad (8)$$

$$S_{\text{mcs}} = \min(\text{mcs}_{\text{adapt}}, 1.0) \quad (9)$$

$$S_{\text{latency}} = \frac{1}{\max(\text{buffer ratio}, 0.1)} \quad (10)$$

in which, E_{baseline} is the average value of experimental datasets, E_{UL} and E_{DL} are current downlink/uplink energy consumption, respectively. If the energy consumed by the system is less than the baseline energy, the EEF value will be greater than 1, indicating that it is more energy-efficient than the traditional system. Meanwhile, the QoS_rate is a linear combination of the corresponding weighted values w of different KPIs, and the value of 0.5, 0.3, 0.2 are parameters tuning based on existing goals and use weighted average to get comprehensive QoS satisfaction.

As shown in Fig. 3, the Dual-layer RL algorithm is outperformed than all control algorithms in terms of total throughput, reaching 13.12 Mbps, which is much higher than the suboptimal Single-Layer DQN (8.43 Mbps) and max throughput (8.26 Mbps). This result shows that the Dual-layer RL algorithm can achieve collaborative optimization at the global network resource scheduling level and local link level, which significantly improves the overall data transmission capability of the system. The dual-layer RL architecture effectively alleviates the limitations of the global optimization of the single-layer strategy, so that the system can still maintain high throughput performance under high load conditions. In terms of user average speed, Dual-layer RL also achieved the optimal result of 2.62 Mbps, which outperformed Single-Layer DQN (2.11 Mbps) and max throughput (2.07 Mbps). This result shows that while pursuing the overall performance improvement of the system, Dual-layer RL can take into account the rate fairness among users, allowing more users to obtain higher service rates. This feature is of great significance to improving the quality of user experience.

Furthermore, Dual-layer RL achieved 1.14 on energy efficiency factor, which was slightly lower than the highest value of min energy strategy of 1.43, but was significantly higher than max throughput (0.77) and Single-Layer DQN (0.84). This result shows that Dual-layer RL does not show strong energy

utilization efficiency and balance capabilities while achieving high performance. This performance-energy consumption-taking feature provides the possibility for its application in green communication scenarios.

Finally, in terms of QoS satisfaction rates, both Dual-layer RL and max throughput reached 1.00, better than Single-Layer DQN (0.91) and QoS optimized (0.65). This shows that Dual-layer RL can fully meet the user's service quality constraints while achieving high-performance transmission, and has strong robustness and stability.

Overall, Dual-layer RL performs excellently in three dimensions: system performance (throughput, user rate), service assurance (QoS), and resource utilization (energy efficiency), while other methods often only gain advantages in a single dimension. For example, max throughput is relatively high, but has low energy efficiency; min energy is most efficient, but has extremely poor throughput and QoS performance. In contrast, Dual-layer RL achieves a triple balance of performance, energy efficiency and service quality, fully verifying its application feasibility and practical value as a scalable, efficient and adaptive resource scheduling strategy in future intelligent wireless networks. Runtime cost is dominated by lower-level neural network inference; for a fixed architecture, inference scales with model size. Training can be performed offline/asynchronously at the Non-RT RIC, while the Near-RT RIC executes lightweight forward inference to meet low-latency requirements.

V. CONCLUSION

This work investigates energy-efficient resource management for communication systems based on the O-RAN architecture. Due to the complexity and dynamic nature of modern communication systems, traditional optimization methods face increasing challenges in achieving efficient resource allocation. We propose a two-stage decision-making approach based on hierarchical deep reinforcement learning (HDRL) to derive energy-aware resource scheduling policies. An upper-level reward function focusing on global resource allocation and a lower-level reward function incorporating throughput, QoS, and energy efficiency are designed. The proposed HDRL framework provides a structured way to integrate algorithmic decision-making with practical resource management considerations. The core innovation lies in the careful design of mathematical functions that transform discrete dataset metrics into continuous optimization signals, achieving intelligent adaptive network performance optimization. Finally, the evaluation results indicate that the proposed approach can improve energy efficiency while maintaining competitive throughput performance under the considered settings. Future work will focus on extending the proposed framework to explicitly model cross-layer coordination mechanisms and control-loop interactions.

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Fig. 3: Network KPI performance of different scheduler of O-RAN.

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